

Optimal Shipbuilding Production Planning through Modeling and Simulation of Complex Rules and Space Constraints

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Abstract. The subassembly process within the shipbuilding process can be classified as a typical job shop process, which is subject to various constraints in terms of the area that can be occupied and the facility and personnel available for the manufacture of the components. Consequently, the efficacy of the subassembly process is contingent on the expertise and knowledge of skilled workers. Therefore, it is challenging to ascertain whether the optimal production plan is being formulated and executed. The previous study proposes a production planning support method that takes into account the unique circumstances of the subassembly process. This method involves modeling the subassembly process using a discrete event system and simulation using the system. To this end, the authors integrated the characteristics inherent to the subassembly process into the shipbuilding process modeling method that had been developed by the authors in a previous study. The validity of the method proposed in this study was confirmed by comparing the production plan created by the proposed model with a plan created by a skilled engineer for the same subassembly process. It was also demonstrated that adjusting design variables, such as the area of the workplace and the worker assignment, enables the generation of more rational and efficient production plans. These findings suggest that the proposed method can provide practical support for decision-making in production planning for shipbuilding.

1 Introduction

Precise production management is essential for improving productivity and strengthening cost competitiveness in shipbuilding. However, shipbuilding processes involve complex interactions among workers, products, tasks, and facilities, making it extremely difficult to create production plans that comprehensively considers all these elements. In recent years, with the development of digital technologies, the effectiveness of utilizing modeling and simulation in shipbuilding process management has been widely recognized [1-3]. By constructing a model of the target production process in cyberspace and returning the simulation results to the field, it can support decision-making in production planning and field management [4,5]. The authors proposed a modeling method that describes a plan in terms of four elements as a generic method for modeling production planning and developed a discrete event simulation that generates a production plan by inputting the process represented by authors' model [6]. Furthermore, the effectiveness of this method was validated through its application to a shipyard production process [7].

On the other hand, the subassembly process is classified as a typical job-shop type process and is subjected various constraints in terms of area that can be occupied and the facility and personnel available for the manufacture of the components. Since the target products differ in shape and size, field workers adjust operations based on their knowledge and experience to accommodate these variations. As a result, it is difficult for production managers to appropriately evaluate the rationality of current production activities. In addition, although the subassembly process offers a wide range of flexibility, it is difficult to accurately assess the impact of changes to specific parts of the process. The objective of this study is to support production managers in their production planning by extending the previous method to accommodate the subassembly process and by using modeling and simulation that reflect the characteristics of the field.

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2 Modeling of subassembly processes

This chapter describes a modeling method for shipbuilding processes based on the four elements proposed by authors [6], taking into account the constraint of work area, available facility, and human resources specific to the targeted subassembly process.

2.1 Modeling method for the subassembly process

The modeling method for the subassembly process is based on and extended from the previous study [6]. In the previous study, the target construction process is modeled as a network structure, which consists of four elements: (1) Product: representing the product, (2) Workflow: representing the tasks to produce the product, (3) Workplace: representing the workplaces or facilities, and (4) Team: representing field workers. Figure 1 shows the components of each element represented by nodes, links, and properties based on graph theory [9].

Figure 1. Shipbuilding processes described by the four elements [6].

In this study, "Required Capacity" in Product is defined as the two-dimensional floor area needed to place the product in the workplace. The shape of each product is approximated as a rectangle, and its area is calculated based on the minimum bounding rectangle. Stacking of a product with other products is not allowed. "Capacity" in Workplace is defined as the total area where products can be placed in the workplace.

Factory rules are guidelines for improving the efficiency with which workers operate products of various shapes and sizes taking into account the constraints of each factory. These rules include very detailed and irregular cases. How detailed the rules should be considered in the model and how detailed the products and tasks should be managed depend largely on the judgment of the production managers. To reflect factory rules in the model shown in Figure 1, it is first necessary to conduct interviews with production managers to organize the required product level, task level, and the factory rules to be adopted. Then, based on the organized information, each component of Figure 1 is clearly defined, and factory rules are reflected in the model.

2.2 Process simulation Algorithm

This section presents the simulation algorithm that reproduces production activities by updating task states in the defined model at each time step (t), using a discrete event system. Four task states are defined as follows. None: cannot start, Ready: can start, Working: in progress, Finished: completed. The execution of tasks continues to repeat operations until all tasks reach the Finished state.

1. Extract of tasks in Ready or Working state.
2. Place the products depending on the extracted tasks in the workplace.
3. Assign workers and facilities to tasks related to the products in the workplace.

4. Update the remaining workload and state of tasks

This study considers the space constraints of the subassembly process by including the rule for the product's workplace placement in the second operation described above.

- For tasks in Finished state: remove the product from the workplace where it was placed at time $t - 1$.
- For tasks in Ready state: place the product in the target workplace. However, if there is no capacity in the target workplace, the product is not placed. A workplace is judged to be available for placement if the "Required Capacity" of the product to be newly placed is less than the total "Required Capacity" of the products already placed from the "Capacity" of the target workplace.
- For tasks in Working state: place the product in the same workplace as at time $t - 1$.

2.3 Model-based production planning method

As shown in Figure 2, this section explains the method for deriving more rational and efficient production plans by using modeling and simulation mentioned in previous section.

Figure 2. Model-based production planning method.

1. Create a modified model of the target process, setting some components of the current model as design variables.
2. Input the modified model and run a simulation.
3. Calculate multiple KPIs based on the simulation results.
4. Quantitatively compare the current and modified models using each KPI and determine the optimal values for the design variables.

KPI (Key Performance Indicator) is an indicator to quantitatively evaluate a proposed production plan. Typical examples include the overall lead time of the plan, worker's operation rate, worker's waiting time, and product's residence time.

3 Case study for actual shipyards

In this case study, a model of the current production activities in a subassembly process within a shipyard is developed. For subassembly process in the shipyard targeted here, there is the actual performance records of according to the current production plan, and this comparison with the simulation results based on this system will be discussed later.

3.1 Characteristics of the target subassembly process and factory rules

Figure 3 shows the layout of the subassembly process and the actual operating conditions. The basic mechanism of the subassembly process is to place subassembly members as densely as possible in a workplace, with the parts fixed in place and workers assigned to each task taking turns. Based on interviews with skilled production managers, the requirements for product management in the subassembly process are summarized as follows.

- All subassembly members whose parent product is the same assembly block are placed in the workplace at the same time as much as possible.
- All subassembly members whose parent product is the same assembly block do not need to determine the order in which subassembly members begins.
- The orientation and position of the subassembly members on the workplace is the judgment of the field workers.

Based on interviews with skilled field workers and production managers, factory rules considering work convenience and restrictions are organized as follows.

- Rule1: Since most of the assembly blocks for starboard and port sides are symmetrical and similar in shape, all subassembly members for both sides are placed in the workplace at once to improve work efficiency.
- Rule2: If subs include preceding subassembly members, the construction of the subassembly members cannot begin until all the preceding subs are completed.
- Rule3: When an assembly block consists of many subassembly members, placing all subassembly members at once delays the placement of subassembly members for other assembly blocks. Therefore, the subassembly members are placed in two times.

Figure 3. Shipyard Layout & Photos.

3.2 Modeling of the target subassembly process

Figure 4 shows the target subassembly process model. This section details how the field process was represented according to the four models in Figure 1.

Figure 4. Production model of subassembly stage.

3.2.1 Modeling workplaces and facilities

The location where the subassembly stage evaluated in this study area consists of four jigs for fabrication and a large area as shown in Figure 3. The jigs for fabrication are used for large and complicated subassembly members called “3D subassembly members”, while the large area is for the construction of simple subassembly members called “General subassembly members”. In the field, the production management is divided according to the different types of subassembly members. Workplace in Figure 1 is defined as “General Sub Place” for the area without jigs and “3D Sub Place” for the area with jigs. "Capacity" of General Sub Place is defined as the area [m²] enclosed by Jigs 1-4, the storage area, and the walking paths, while "Capacity" of 3D Sub Place is defined as total area [m²] of the four jigs. "Facility" installed in each workplace and "Target Task" that each facility can perform are also defined, and the necessary data for modeling workplaces and facilities is summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Data for modeling workplaces and facilities.

Workplace	Capacity[m ²]	Facility	Target Task
General Sub Place	420	Tool H1	G Distribute
		Tool T1	G Fit
		Tool W1	G Weld
		Tool W2	G Weld
		Tool W3	G Weld
3D Sub Place	184	Tool H2	3D Distribute
		Tool T2	3D Fit
		Tool W4	3D Weld
		Tool W5	3D Weld
		Tool W6	3D Weld

3.2.2 Modeling products

Product in Figure 1 is defined as a set of subs whose parent product is the same assembly block, rather than individual subassembly members, considering the production manager's requirements for product management. Based on this definition, we applied the factory rules to model the products.

- Rule1: The set of subassembly members corresponding to the starboard side assembly block (Name ends with S) and the port side assembly block (Name ends with P) is defined as the same Product.
- Rule2: The set of preceding subassembly members placed in the workplace is defined as "1st Group" Product, and the set of following subs placed is defined as "2nd Group" Product.
- Rule3: If the total area of the set of subassembly members exceeds 400 [m²], the set is divided into two times, defined as "1st Group" Product and "2nd Group" Product.

The data for modeling products is summarized in Table 2. The products listed in the table are defined by extracting subs constructed in the two weeks of the work performance record and applying the above modeling method. "Required Capacity" of the product is calculated as the rectangular area [m²] surrounding the base plate, based on the maximum length [m] and maximum width [m] of the base plate obtained from the design data.

Table 2. Data for modeling products.

Product	Group	Required Capacity[m²]
AA	1 st Group	27
	2 nd Group	27
ABPS	—	44
ACPS	—	51
ADP	1 st Group	223
	2 nd Group	223
ADS	1 st Group	217
	2 nd Group	217
AEPS	—	57
AF	1 st Group	89
	2 nd Group	89
AGPS	1 st Group	67
	2 nd Group	67
AH	—	54
AIPS	—	50
BAPS	—	70
BBPS	1 st Group	126
	2 nd Group	126
BC	—	47
BD	—	46

3.2.3 Modeling tasks

Based on the analysis of workers' performance records, we defined "Task" of Workflow in Figure 1 by dividing the works from the distribution of parts on the workplace to the removal of subassembly members from the workplace at the timing when workers are changed. The analysis revealed that in all subassembly members, distribution, fitting, and welding are performed on the front side of the base plate. If necessary, distribution, fitting, welding, and straightening are performed on the back side of the base plate. The backside work may not occur, or the procedure is not uniform. And even for the same tasks, different workers are assigned to general subassembly members and 3D subassembly members. Based on the above, we define the tasks related to the general subassembly members as "G Distribution", "G Fit", "G Weld", and define the tasks related to the 3D subassembly members as "3D Distribute", "3D Fit", "3D Weld". The necessary data for modeling of the process is summarized in Table 3. "Workload" of each task is set based on the actual data obtained from the factory, and the unit is [man-minute]. The "Dependency between Tasks" for each product is in the order of 1st Task, 2nd Task, and 3rd Task. For products that are placed in the workplace in two times, a constraint is defined that 1st Task of the 2nd Group starts after the 3rd Task of 1st Group is completed based on the factory rule.

Table 3. Data for modeling tasks.

Product	Group	1st Task		2nd Task		3rd Task	
		Name	Workload	Name	Workload	Name	Workload
AA	1 st Group	G Distribution	24	G Fit	264	G Weld	411
	2 nd Group	G Distribution	99	G Fit	312	G Weld	234
ABPS	—	G Distribution	57	G Fit	105	G Weld	906
ACPS	—	G Distribution	237	G Fit	420	G Weld	783
ADP	1 st Group	G Distribution	168	G Fit	378	G Weld	267
	2 nd Group	G Distribution	327	G Fit	597	G Weld	618
ADS	1 st Group	G Distribution	138	G Fit	216	G Weld	309
	2 nd Group	G Distribution	330	G Fit	564	G Weld	1107

AEPS	—	G Distribution	180	G Fit	255	G Weld	750
AF	1 st Group	G Distribution	48	G Fit	111	G Weld	3
	2 nd Group	G Distribution	285	G Fit	456	G Weld	687
AGPS	1 st Group	G Distribution	183	G Fit	165	G Weld	42
	2 nd Group	G Distribution	168	G Fit	591	G Weld	2952
AH	—	G Distribution	318	G Fit	1059	G Weld	1335
AIPS	—	G Distribution	147	G Fit	153	G Weld	378
BAPS	—	3D Distribution	186	3D Fit	618	3D Weld	1203
BBPS	1 st Group	3D Distribution	285	3D Fit	1209	3D Weld	810
	2 nd Group	3D Distribution	234	3D Fit	1479	3D Weld	3588
BC	—	3D Distribution	105	3D Fit	366	3D Weld	906
BD	—	3D Distribution	129	3D Fit	837	3D Weld	933

3.2.4 Modeling workers

Based on the analysis of workers' performance records, seven workers (Worker 1 to Worker 7) are defined as “Worker” in Team in Figure 1. Worker 1 is responsible for the allocation of both general and 3D subassembly members. Worker 2 is responsible for fitting only for general subassembly members. Worker 3 is responsible for fitting only for 3D subassembly members. Worker 4 is responsible for welding only for general subassembly members. Worker 5 and Worker 6 are responsible for welding for both general and 3D subassembly members. Worker 7 is responsible for welding only for 3D subassembly members. The data for modeling these workers are summarized in Table 4. For example, “Target Task” of Worker 1 is G Distribution and 3D Distribution and the “Target Facility” is Tool H1 and Tool H2. The “Skill Value”, which indicates the work efficiency for a worker, is set to 1.0, meaning that it takes 1.0 [minute] to complete a task with a workload of 1.0 [man-minute].

Table 4. Data for modeling workers.

Worker	Target Task	Target Facility	Skill Value
Worker 1	G Distribution, 3D Distribution	Tool H1, Tool H2	1.0
Worker 2	G Fit	Tool T1	1.0
Worker 3	3D Fit	Tool T2	1.0
Worker 4	G Weld	Tool W1, Tool W2, Tool W3	1.0
Worker 5	G Weld, 3D Weld	Tool W1, Tool W2, Tool W3 Tool W4, Tool W5, Tool W6	1.0
Worker 6	G Weld, 3D Weld	Tool W1, Tool W2, Tool W3 Tool W4, Tool W5, Tool W6	1.0
Worker 7	3D Weld	Tool W4, Tool W5, Tool W6	1.0

3.3 Simulation Running

By inputting the data for each process modeled in section 3.2 into pDESy [7], an open-source discrete event simulation system developed by the authors, the production plan is obtained. Left figure in Figure 5 shows the Gantt chart for each product and right figure in Figure 5 shows the Gantt chart for each worker. In both figures, the colored sections represent the execution of tasks. The horizontal axis indicates the time steps [h], and the vertical axis represents each product or worker. Figure 6 shows changes in occupied area by products in General Sub Place and 3D Sub Place, during the overall lead time. The horizontal axis indicates time step [h], the vertical axis indicates the total area occupied by products [m²], and the red dashed line indicates the capacity of each workplace. Each product is shown in a different color. The graph confirms that the products are placed within the capacity of the workplaces, indicating that the space constraints have been properly considered in this model.

Figure 5. Gantt chart for products (left figure) and Gantt chart for workers (right figure).

Figure 6. Changes in Occupied Area: General Sub (left figure) and 3D Sub (right figure).

The evaluation indicators calculated based on the simulation results are summarized in Table 5. LT is the overall lead time, Total RT is the total residence time that products stayed in the workplace without working, Total WT is the total waiting time of workers and OR Index is the standard deviation of the worker operation rates. While LT refers to the time between when the first product is placed in the workplace and when the last product is removed from the workplace, VT represents the validity time during which all workers have any tasks. Total WT and OR Index are calculated for both time periods.

Table 5. Simulation results: KPIs

Lead Time (LT)	131.8 _[h]
Total Residence Time for Products (Total RT)	147.1 _[h]
Total Waiting Time for Workers in VT (Total WT VT)	220 _[h]
Operation Rate Index in VT (OR Index VT)	15.2 _[%]
Total Waiting Time for Workers in LT (Total WT LT)	387.7 _[h]
Operation Rate Index in VT (OR Index LT)	14.8 _[%]

3.4 Comparison between the simulation results and the actual performance records

Figure 7 shows a comparison between the simulation results and the actual performance records. In this figure, the colored sections represent the simulation results showing the operating hours of each product. This simulation reflects the scheduling information that considers the factory's operation period, such as from 8:00 AM to 5:00 PM, as well as weekends and holidays. The dashed arrows represent the actual performance records from when each product is placed in the workplace until it is removed. The gray areas indicate non-operating period of the factory, and the red circles represent the required dates for each product from the block assembly factory which corresponds to the next process.

Figure 7. Comparison of Simulation and Actual Results.

Comparing the start time and the end time, the start time is 8:00 on June 15th for both the actual data and the simulation results. The end time is 12:00 on July 4th for the actual data, and 14:27 on July 4th for the simulation results. There is no significant difference between the actual data and simulated results for the construction period of all products. However, when each product is compared individually, the simulation results show overall tendency that the start time of placement to be earlier than the actual results. This is because the simulation was calculated to maximize the use of available space of the workplace for product placement compared to the actual results.

Comparing the required dates and the simulation results, almost all the products are delivered on time. However, product AGPS and AIPS are delayed against the required dates. Since these products manage all the subassembly members related to the assembly blocks on the starboard and port sides at once, they are constructed based on the earlier requested date, which may cause some delays. This point is within a certain acceptable range considering the characteristics of the factory rules. The simulation results were shared with the production managers in evaluated shipyard in this study to confirm the validity of the plan that can be used for the field work instructions.

4 Study of optimal production planning

In the subassembly stage in this study, a more appropriate production plan will be studied using a model-based production planning method in this study, considering the trend toward multi-skilled workers and a review of how to utilize workplaces and surrounding space.

4.1 Design for workplace area

"Capacity" of General Sub Place and 3D Sub Place is used as design variables. Appropriate workplace area is derived based on the current workplace as 100%. The upper limit of the change rate (170%) is set where the workplace can be expanded by using the storage area and aisles around as the workplace. The lower limit of the change rate (70%) is set based on the minimum workplace area where the product with the largest "Required Capacity" can be placed in. 5% intervals is adopted as the change rate of the workplace area where the number of product placements changes. The simulation results of these modified models are compared based on two evaluation indicators: Total waiting time of Workers in VT (Total WT VT[h]) and Total Residence Time for Products (Total RT[h]). The results are shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Optimal workplace area for evaluated subassembly stage.

The simulation results show that a larger workplace area allows more products to be placed at once, but the waiting time of products increases due to the lack of workers, and the rotation rate of the workplace decreases. On the other hand, a smaller workplace area tends to reduce the waiting time of products and improve the rotation rate of the workplace, but the waiting time of workers tends to increase due to the limited number of products that can be placed in the workplace. This clearly shows the tradeoffs associated with the change of workplace area. The closer to the origin of the graph, the better the results for both waiting time of products and workers. Figure 8 shows that if the current workplace area is expanded by 10% (the change rate of the workplace area is set to 110%), the workload among workers will be balanced and more efficient production plan can be derived.

4.2 Design for worker assignment plan

The bottleneck survey is conducted for the current worker assignment plan, and a new assignment plan is developed based on the survey results. The bottleneck survey quantitatively analyzes the impact of a decrease in work efficiency for each worker, from Worker 1 to Worker 7, on the overall production plan. Modified models are created by reducing “Skill Value” — an indicator of each worker's efficiency — from 1.0 to 0.5, and simulation is conducted for each model. The simulation results are compared and evaluated using multiple evaluation indicators. Table 6 shows the rankings determined by the deviation of each indicator from its default value. The model with the smallest deviation is ranked 1st, while the model with the largest deviation is ranked 6th. The total score is calculated by summing the rankings across all evaluation indicators. The results show that Worker 2, with a total of 35, has the largest impact on the overall production plan, while Worker 7, with a total of 11, has the smallest impact.

Table 6. Result of the bottleneck survey for evaluated subassembly stage.

Evaluation Indicator	Default	Worker 1	Worker 2	Worker 3	Worker 4	Worker 5&6	Worker 7
LT _[h]	131.8	178.4	210.8	170.5	139.2	141.8	134.8
Total RT _[h]	147.1	121.8	240.9	149.3	157.8	161.5	151
Total WT VT _[h]	220	296.5	255.2	237.6	214.3	214.7	210
OR Index VT _[%]	15.2	19.5	23	21	13.7	12.6	14.3
Total WT LT _[h]	387.7	653.3	846.6	583.4	391.4	403.7	383.8
OR Index LT _[%]	14.8	13.8	22.2	20.6	17.3	15.8	14.1
Rank Sum	—	22	35	24	16	18	11

This survey revealed that the fitting process of General Sub Place in charge of Worker 2 is the bottleneck, while the welding process of 3D Sub Place in charge of Worker 7 has a margin. Based on the above, the following five modified plans are made to review the current worker assignment plan.

- Plan 1: Eliminate Worker 7.
- Plan 2: Eliminate Worker 4.
- Plan 3: Assign Worker 2 and Worker 3 to both workplaces.
- Plan 4: Eliminate Worker 7, Assign Worker 2 and Worker 3 to both workplaces.
- Plan 5: Eliminate Worker 4, Assign Worker 2 and Worker 3 to both workplaces.

In the current assignment plan, Worker 2 is responsible for fitting only for General Sub Place, and Worker 4 is responsible for fitting only for 3D Sub Place. On the other hand, Plans 3 to 5 aim to promote multi-skilled workers by having workers 2 and 4 in charge of both General Sub Place and 3D Sub Place. In addition, Plans 1, 2, 4, and 5 aim to reduce one surplus worker and reassign him to a different process.

Table 7 compares the simulation results for the current assignment plan and each modified plan based on several evaluation indicators. Plan 4 exhibits the greatest number of improved evaluation indicators among all modified plans compared to the current assignment plan. By enabling both Worker 2 and Worker 3 to work simultaneously on the bottleneck, fitting process at the General Sub Place, the overall lead time can be reduced. Furthermore, the elimination of Worker 7 helps achieve a more balanced distribution of workload among the remaining workers and reduces their waiting times.

Table 7. Comparison of assignment change plans.

Evaluation Indicator	Current Plan	Plan 1	Plan 2	Plan 3	Plan 4	Plan 5
LT _[h]	131.8	141.6	157.2	124.1	128.3	158.5
Total RT _[h]	147.1	152.7	198.8	156.2	173.3	234.5
Total WT VT _[h]	220	169.6	195.2	136.2	172.3	143.9
OR Index VT _[%]	15.2	12.7	19.5	15.5	13.5	22.4
Total WT LT _[h]	387.7	315.1	408.8	333.3	235.1	416.1
OR Index LT _[%]	14.8	7.8	11.4	15.2	9.9	17.9

5 Conclusion

This study developed a modeling and simulation system that incorporates space constraints and complex rules to support optimal production planning of subassembly process, considering complex field characteristics. First, we created a model of the current production activities in a subassembly process within a shipyard and compared with the actual results to validate the proposed modeling method. Then, we examined whether a more efficient plan could be created in comparison with current production plan by using a model-based production planning method and obtained the following findings.

- In the case study regard to the design for area of the workplaces, two indicators were adopted: “Total waiting time of Workers” and “Total Residence Time for Products”, which are in a trade-off relationship. The analysis showed that expanding workplace area 10% larger than the current size would balance the workload among workers and derive a more efficient production plan.
- In the case study regard to the design for the worker assignment, based on the bottleneck survey, a new assignment plan was adopted to eliminate a welding worker, and to assign two fitting workers to both workplaces. This new assignment plan can shorten the overall lead time, and the waiting time of workers compared to the current assignment plan, as well as reduce the number of workers.

The above results show that if the target production process can be appropriately represented as a simulation model, it is possible to compare the current production model with modified model patterns and derive a more optimal production plan. In the conventional manual method based on experience, it is difficult to accurately evaluate the impact of changes in individual elements on the entire process, and the method relies heavily on trial

and error. On the other hand, the model-based production planning method proposed in this study enables us to quantitatively evaluate the impact of changes in each element in advance and to make more rational decisions. Therefore, it can be concluded that this method is an effective approach to support the decision making of production managers in shipbuilding project management.

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